

Prediction of Toe Stability in Rubble Mound Breakwaters Using Artificial Neural Networks

Ali Jamali Rovesht¹, Ali Mohammadi¹, Mehdi Shafieefar²

1- MSc. Student, Faculty of Civil and Environmental Engineering, Tarbiat Modares University, Tehran, Iran

2- Professor, Faculty of Civil and Environmental Engineering, Tarbiat Modares University, Tehran, Iran

shafiee@modares.ac.ir

Abstract

Rubble mound breakwaters with concrete and stone armor units are essential in coastal engineering, protecting against wave action and sediment transport. Stability of toe in these structures is critical, supporting the armor layer and preventing scour, thus influencing the breakwater's performance and longevity. This study advances toe stability prediction using an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) approach. Experimental data from laboratory tests on breakwaters with concrete, stone, and composite toes, conducted mainly in deep water conditions, were used to train and validate the ANN model. Featuring a hidden layer and an advanced optimization algorithm, the model effectively captures complex, non-linear relationships. The ANN's performance was compared to empirical methods using metrics such as the correlation coefficient of determination (R^2), root mean square error (RMSE), mean absolute error (MAE), mean squared error (MSE), correlation coefficient (CC), and normalized bias (nBias). Results demonstrated the ANN's superior accuracy, with higher R^2 and lower RMSE, MAE, MSE, and nBias values, highlighting the significant potential of neural networks for enhancing toe stability analysis in breakwater design.

Keywords: Rubble mound breakwater, toe stability, concrete toe, artificial neural network

1- INTRODUCTION

Rubble mound breakwaters are key structures in coastal engineering, primarily designed and constructed to protect ports, shorelines, and coastal facilities from hazards caused by waves and sediment displacement. Rubble mound breakwaters exhibit multiple failure modes, with one of the most critical being the instability of the toe (Figure 1). The toe provides foundational support to the armor layer, mitigates scour caused by wave action, and ensures the overall structural integrity of the breakwater. The level of a breakwater toe in the water is a crucial feature influencing its intricate hydrodynamic performance. This behavior can differ considerably between shallow and deep water environments, complicating the prediction of toe stability. Numerous laboratory experiments with various objectives and conditions have been conducted to investigate the stability of breakwater toes and the factors affecting them. These studies have led to the development of several empirical formulas [1-6]. However, the significant scatter of the results obtained from these formulas is primarily due to the use of limited datasets in their extraction. In most experiments conducted to assess the

stability of breakwater toes, the extent of toe damage is typically measured using the parameter N_{od} . This parameter represents the number of displaced or washed-away toe stones within a strip of width D_{n50} .

The values of N_{od} equal to 0.5, 2, and 4 respectively indicate the onset of damage (acceptable stability), acceptable damage with some flattening of the toe, and complete failure with full flattening of the toe [6]. Nevertheless, the N_{od} parameter itself has been the subject of extensive research, which is beyond the scope of this study [7, 8]. Given the outstanding performance of artificial neural networks (ANN) in research related to rubble mound breakwaters [9-11], this study proposes an innovative approach for predicting the stability of breakwater toes using these networks. A comprehensive dataset has been compiled, which includes data from previous studies and new data obtained from experiments conducted in the Marine Structures Laboratory at Tarbiat Modares University. This dataset covers a wide range of conditions, including stone and concrete toes in deep-water environments. By leveraging the predictive capabilities of artificial neural networks, this study has developed a model that significantly improves the prediction accuracy of toe stability compared to existing empirical formulas.

The structure of the article is organized as follows: The second section offers a detailed review of prior research on breakwater toe stability and the empirical formulas developed for its prediction. The third section outlines the dataset compiled for the study and the parameters analyzed. The fourth section details the methodology used to develop the artificial neural network (ANN) model. The fifth section explains the statistical parameters employed to evaluate model performance. The sixth section compares the ANN model's performance against existing empirical formulas, demonstrating its superior accuracy. Finally, the seventh section summarizes the key findings and concludes the study.

Figure 1 - failure modes of Rubble mound breakwater [12]

2- REVIEW OF PREVIOUS STUDIES

Gerding [6] pioneering work presented a relationship between the toe stability number ($N_s = \frac{H_s}{\Delta D_{n50}}$) and the toe depth normalized by the stone size ($\frac{h_t}{D_{n50}}$). This formula is as follows:

$$N_{od} = \left(\frac{\frac{H_s}{\Delta D_{n50}}}{0.24 \frac{h_t}{D_{n50}} + 1.6} \right)^{6.67} \quad (1)$$

where h_t is the water depth above the toe, D_{n50} is the nominal stone diameter, and Δ is the relative density of the rock materials. This formula was primarily developed based on experiments conducted in shallow water conditions with high waves and did not take into account key parameters such as water depth or wave steepness (S_{op}), which created limitations in its application.

van der Meer [2], by analysing Gerding [6] data and observing the dispersion of results and the unrealistic nature of the calculated stone diameter (D_{n50}) for deep water conditions, proposed a modified relationship that took the water depth (h) parameter into account:

$$N_{od} = \left(\frac{\frac{H_s}{\Delta D_{n50}}}{6.2 \left(\frac{h_t}{h} \right)^{2.7} + 2} \right)^{6.67} \quad (2)$$

Burcharth and Liu [1] developed a formula for toe composed of cubic blocks:

$$N_{od} = \left(\left(0.63 \frac{H_s}{\Delta D_{n50}} \right)^{-1} + 0.4 \left(\frac{h_t}{H_s} \right) \right)^{6.67} \quad (3)$$

This relationship was specifically designed for cubic blocks and its application is limited to this type of toes. Ebbens [8] conducted experiments on various seabed slopes (1:50, 1:20, 1:10), different water depths, and irregular waves to investigate the effects of the foreshore slope and wave steepness. Muttray [4] with a theoretical approach based on force balance and the concept of critical velocity, developed a formula that utilized data from regular Markle [13], irregular Gerding [6] waves, and Ebbens [8] :

$$N_{od} = \left(\frac{H_s}{\Delta D_{n50}} \left(0.58 - 0.17 \left(\frac{h_t}{H_s} \right) \right) \right)^3 \quad (4)$$

This formula limited applicability for $\left(\frac{h_t}{H_s} < 3 \right)$ and its conservative nature, it had limited practical use.

Van Gent and van der Werf [3], focusing on the effect of height and dimensions of the toe, conducted experiments with a foreshore slope of 1:30, irregular waves, and toes with thickness (2 to 4 D_{n50}) and width (3 to 9 D_{n50}). Their proposed formula included the thickness of the toe (t_t), the width of the toe (B_t), and the characteristic wave celerity (\hat{u}_δ) (based on linear wave theory):

$$N_{od} = C_1 \left(\frac{B_t}{H_s} \right)^{C_2} \left(\frac{t_t}{H_s} \right)^{C_3} \left(\frac{H_s}{\Delta D_{n50}} \right)^{C_4} \left(\frac{\hat{u}_\delta}{\sqrt{gH_s}} \right)^{C_5} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{With } \hat{u}_\delta = \frac{\pi H_s}{T_{m-1,0}} \frac{1}{\sinh kh_t} \quad (6)$$

$$\text{and } k = \frac{2\pi}{L_{m-1,0}} = \frac{2\pi}{\frac{g T^2}{2\pi} m^{-1,0}} \quad (7)$$

This study showed that increasing the thickness and width of the toe and the wave slope reduces stability, but wider toes can withstand higher levels of damage.

Van Gent and van der Werf [3] proposed the formula (eq. 5) with calibrated coefficients: $C_1=0.032$, $C_2=0.3$, $C_3=1$, $C_4=3$ and $C_5=1$. These coefficients were calibrated based on his experiments and allow for re-calibration using more comprehensive datasets. The validity of this relationship is limited to toes with a thickness of 10% to 30% of the water depth in front of the structure, a 1:2 armor layer slope, and a water depth in front of the toe between 1.2 to 4.5 times the wave height.

Etemad-Shahidi, et al. [5] conducted a study based on a comprehensive dataset of previous experiments with the aim of developing a new and precise formula for predicting the stability of breakwater toes. They developed this formula using physical reasoning and regression analysis:

$$N_{od} = \left(\frac{(N_s - 1.2) \left(\frac{B_t}{H_s}\right)^{\frac{1}{10}} S_{om}^{-\frac{1}{6}} \left(\frac{h_t}{h}\right)^{-\frac{7}{4}}}{11.2(1 - 3.7m)} \right)^{2.5} \quad (8)$$

Where m is the foreshore slope. This relationship, considering the effects of key parameters, showed better performance compared to existing empirical relationships. They developed the proposed relationship for common design conditions with a wide range of applications (such as $0.4 < \frac{h_t}{h} < 0.9$ and $0.5 < N_{od} < 4$).

These formulas have been developed based on diverse datasets that include regular waves Markle [13], irregular waves [3, 6, 8], various bed slopes (1:50 to 1:10), and water depths ranging from very shallow to relatively deep. The definitions of damage also vary; Gerding [6] considered only washed stones, while later studies such as Ebbens [8] and Van Gent and van der Werf [3] counted all displaced stones (whether remaining in the toe or not). These differences make direct comparison of relationships difficult and highlight the need for further testing under diverse conditions and the development of more precise methods for predicting toe stability.

3- DATASET AND ASSOCIATED PARAMETERS

The dataset used for developing the artificial neural network (ANN) model to predict the stability of the breakwater toe included 573 laboratory data points collected from various studies. Ebbens [8] presented 93 data from a study that included a literature review and scaled model tests. This study was conducted in collaboration with the Coastal Engineering Department of Delta Marine Consultants (DMC), and the experiments were carried out at DMC's laboratory facilities in Utrecht, Netherlands. Gerding [6] provided 171 data points from a study conducted as part of a master's thesis at the Delft University of Technology. These experiments were conducted at the Delft Hydraulics Laboratory. Van Leeuwen [14] presented 97 data points from experiments conducted in the Fluid Mechanics Laboratory of the Civil Engineering Faculty at Delft University of Technology. Bagheshahi, et al. [15] collected 212 data points from experiments conducted in the two-dimensional wave flume of the Marine Structures Laboratory at Tarbiat Modares University. Table 1 provides a summary of the specifications and range of the laboratory data used in this study.

Table 1 specifications and range of the laboratory data

Item		Gerding [6]	Van Leeuwen [14]	Ebbens [8]	Bagheshahi, et al. [15]
Significant wave height, H_s	[cm]	15.3 - 25.1	9.2 - 21.2	6 - 12	5.2 - 13.7
peak wave period, T_p	[s]	1.5 - 3.6	1.3 - 1.8	1.1 - 2.9	1.1 - 1.8
Seabed slope, m	-	1:20	1:50	1:10 - 1:20 - 1:50	0
Toe height, t_t	[cm]	8 - 22	8 - 15	8	3.5 - 9
Toe width, B_t	[cm]	12 - 30	12	10	7.8 - 23.3
Water depth in the front of the toe, h_m	[cm]	30 - 50	30 - 45	13.3 - 33.9	30.9 - 54.6
Water depth, h	[cm]	70 - 90	50 - 65	48.7 - 69.8	30.9 - 54.6
h_t / h	-	0.2 - 0.5	0.3 - 0.6	0.1 - 0.4	0.4 - 0.7
h / H_s	-	3 - 5.7	2.9 - 6.8	4.1 - 9.4	2.6 - 7.1
Damage level, N_{od}	-	0 - 9.21	0 - 4.7	0.06 - 3.01	0 - 9.53

4- ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORK MODELING AND RESULTS

In this study, artificial neural networks (ANNs) were utilized to predict toe stability. Inspired by biological neural systems, these networks can model complex, non-linear relationships between input features and toe stability. The input features, including H_s , T_p , D_{n50} , d , h_m , m , Δ , α , h_b , h_t , t_t , and B_t , served as the basis for the model. The ANN architecture consisted of a layered structure with input, hidden, and output layers. The model featured two hidden layers with 64 neurons in the first layer and 32 neurons in the second layer. The

ReLU activation function was used to process data and apply weights, enabling the capture of non-linear patterns. The learning process involved forward propagation of data followed by back-propagation to adjust weights, optimizing the model's performance. Hyperparameters, including the number of neurons (64 and 32), ReLU activation function, Adam optimizer, learning rate of 0.001, batch size of 32, 100 epochs, and MSE loss function, were tuned using a random search strategy to enhance prediction accuracy based on initial training results (Figure 2).

Figure 2 Training and Validation Loss Over Epochs

To evaluate the new ANN model's performance, Figure 3 compares observed N_{od} values with predicted ones. The figure clearly shows that the ANN model's predictions are fairly accurate across the entire dataset range. The central line represents perfect agreement between predicted and experimental values. Additionally, Figure 3 demonstrates a high level of symmetry in the ANN model's predictions.

Figure 3 Observations versus ANN predictions for N_{od}

5- PERFORMANCE EVALUATION CRITERIA FOR PREDICTIVE MODELS

The performance of the Artificial Neural Network (ANN) model and various experimental formulas was assessed using a range of statistical metrics, including the correlation coefficient (CC), mean squared error (MSE), mean absolute error (MAE), coefficient of determination (R^2), root mean squared error (RMSE), and normalized bias (nBias). These metrics provide a comprehensive understanding of the models' predictive accuracy. A higher R^2 value indicates a closer fit to the observed data, signifying better model performance. Lower values of MAE, MSE, and RMSE, being error-based measures, suggest higher accuracy, with values nearing zero reflecting minimal prediction errors. The nBias metric measures the average systematic error relative to the actual data, further enriching the evaluation framework.

• The Coefficient of Determination (R^2)

The following formula is used to determine the statistical criterion R^2 :

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (Y_i - \hat{Y}_i)^2}{(Y_i - \bar{Y})^2} \quad (9)$$

• The Mean Absolute Error (MAE)

The average absolute difference between actual and predicted values in the entire dataset is calculated by the statistical criterion known as MAE. The MAE is calculated by taking the sum of the absolute differences for each observation and dividing it by the total number of observations. This measure shows the average degree to which the predictions match the actual values.

$$MAE = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n |Y_i - \hat{Y}_i|}{n} \quad (10)$$

• The Mean Square Error (MSE)

The average squared difference between actual and predicted values in a full data set is measured by the statistical criterion known as MSE. Each observation's squared differences are calculated, added up, and then divided by the total number of observations to accomplish this. The MSE, which gives an overall assessment of how well our predictions, on average, match the true values, is the resultant value.

$$MSE = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (Y_i - \hat{Y}_i)^2}{n} \quad (11)$$

• The Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)

RMSE is a square root of MSE, as is evident from its name.

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (Y_i - \hat{Y}_i)^2}{n}} \quad (12)$$

• Correlation Coefficient (CC)

A measure of statistics called the Correlation Coefficient (CC) measures how strongly and in which direction two variables are related. It typically goes from -1 to 1 and is represented by the symbol r .

$$r = \frac{\sum (X_i - \bar{X})(Y_i - \bar{Y})}{\sqrt{\sum (X_i - \bar{X})^2 \sum (Y_i - \bar{Y})^2}} \quad (13)$$

• Normalized Bias (nBias)

The nBias metric quantifies the systematic error normalized by the actual values, calculated as:

$$nBias = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n Y_i - \hat{Y}_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n |Y_i|} \quad (14)$$

A lower nBias value indicates reduced systematic deviation in predictions.

- **Variable Definitions**

In the equations:

- Y_i : Actual value for observation i.
- \hat{Y}_i : Predicted value for observation i.
- \bar{Y} : Mean of actual values.
- n: Total number of observations.
- X_i : Input variable for observation i.
- \bar{X} : Mean of input values.

6- COMPARISON AMONG THE NEW ANN MODEL AND EMPIRICAL FORMULAS

The aim of this section is to provide a comprehensive comparison between the performance of the artificial neural network (ANN) model and traditional empirical relations in predicting the stability of the breakwater toe. For this purpose, the performance of the ANN model was compared with the empirical relationships proposed in the literature, including the Gerding [6], Etemad-Shahidi, et al. [5], Muttray [4], Van Gent and van der Werf [3], van der Meer [2], Burcharth and Liu [1] formulas. The quantitative evaluation criteria included the coefficient of determination (R^2), root mean square error (RMSE), mean absolute error (MAE), mean square error (MSE), normalized bias (nBias), scatter index (SI), correlation coefficient (CC). These criteria provided the ability to accurately evaluate the precision, stability, and generalizability of the models.

Table 2 reports the quantitative results obtained from the simulations. The results indicate that the ANN model provides more accurate predictions compared to traditional empirical relationships. Specifically, the ANN model had higher (R^2) values (0.811) and lower RMSE and MAE values compared to empirical formulas, indicating its superior ability to fit laboratory data. Additionally, the values of nBias and SI in the ANN model were significantly lower, indicating less dispersion and greater stability of predictions under diverse conditions (such as shallow and deep water, regular and irregular waves, and various types of toe). The correlation coefficient (CC) close to 1 in the ANN model also confirm the high accuracy of this model compared to traditional formulas.

Table 2 Statistical indices for the ANN model versus the other formulas

Models	R^2	RMSE	MAE	MSE	nBias	CC
Gerding [6]	0.160	4.165	1.819	17.345	-0.765	0.400
van der Meer [2]	0.011	11.451	6.265	131.127	-5.874	0.106
Muttray [4]	0.076	5.423	2.307	29.414	-1.379	0.275
Burcharth and Liu [1]	0.162	4.376	1.836	19.148	-0.717	0.402
Etemad-Shahidi, et al. [5]	0.007	13.203	7.843	174.326	-7.766	0.083
Van Gent and van der Werf [3]	0.050	3.306	1.529	10.932	-0.366	0.224
Van Gent and van der Werf [3]_modified	0.058	1.858	1.057	3.452	0.861	0.240
ANN	0.811	0.569	0.363	0.302	0.044	0.902

Figure 4 Scatter plots of observed vs. predicted N_{od} values using empirical formulas

One of the main reasons for the poor performance of traditional empirical formulas in predicting the stability of breakwater toes is their development based on limited laboratory data, primarily for rock toes. However, the initial output of the empirical formulas exhibited poor statistical performance due to highly outlier values. To address this issue and justify the use of these formulas within a specific range of conditions, a limit of 40 was applied to the outputs of the empirical formulas. This constraint helped eliminate extreme outliers, enabling more acceptable results within the initial data range, although it highlights the inherent limitations of these formulas in generalizing to more diverse conditions. In this study, the dataset was expanded by adding new data, including data from Marine Structures Laboratory at Tarbiat Modares University which included tests on rock, concrete, and composite toes at different placement level. This dataset, which primarily focused on deep water conditions, demonstrated that traditional empirical formulas are ineffective in adapting to new conditions and their accuracy significantly decreases. In contrast, the Burcharth and Liu [1] formula, due to its consideration of concrete toes, showed better performance compared to other traditional formulas, but it was still insufficient for practical applications. These findings indicate that traditional empirical formulas, although they have acceptable accuracy within their initial data range, face serious challenges under broader and more diverse conditions. This highlights the necessity of conducting further experiments under various conditions of toe level, diverse geometries, and material combinations (such as concrete blocks, stone, or composite) to develop stronger models in the future.

The effort to improve the Van Gent and van der Werf [3] formula was one of the key achievements of this research. The original version of this formula with initial coefficients ($C_1=0.032$, $C_2=0.3$, $C_3=1$, $C_4=3$, $C_5=1$), which were calibrated for specific laboratory data, had average performance. By recalibrating the coefficients based on the expanded database, the optimized coefficients ($C_1=2.1689$, $C_2=-0.0914$, $C_3=-0.0531$, $C_4=0.7448$, $C_5=1.6093$) were obtained, which improved the modified version with $R^2=0.058$ and $RMSE=1.858$. However, this calibration poses a practical challenge: designers may not have sufficient laboratory data to calibrate the coefficients in their projects, making the use of this formula difficult in practice. This issue highlights the need to develop models with less dependence on local calibration.

Among the models examined, the artificial neural network (ANN) provided the best performance. This model, due to its ability to learn complex and nonlinear patterns from diverse data, including deep and shallow water tests, various geometries, and different toe combinations, predicted toe stability with high accuracy. The high correlation coefficient ($CC=0.902$) and near-zero bias ($nBias=0.044$) in the ANN confirm its significant superiority over traditional models.

7- CONCLUSIONS

A robust neural network-based approach has been developed to predict the stability of breakwater toe. By optimizing the artificial neural network (ANN) through RMSE reduction and strategic data splitting, an effective model was achieved. The results demonstrate that the ANN successfully captures the complex relationships between input parameters and experimental outcomes, leveraging a database from studies by Gerding [6], Ebbens [8], Bagheshahi, et al. [15], and Van Leeuwen [14]. Notably, the ANN outperforms existing formulas, highlighting its potential as a superior tool for modeling toe stability in breakwater design.

It is recommended that further research be conducted to expand and enrich the database, focusing on various geometries and configurations of the toe, while incorporating more advanced methods such as deep learning, hybrid machine learning models, or physics-informed neural networks to enhance the accuracy, robustness, and generalizability of models predicting toe stability in breakwater design.

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